

Maximisation of the use of renewable energy in Rwanda's Energy Mix

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Executive Summary

Energy system modelling serves to assess various scenarios and help in enhancing policymaking. Although, a challenge to initiating energy system modelling in developing nations is the limited access to data, leading to delays. This article offers a dataset that can facilitate the creation of a basic energy system model for Rwanda, serving as a first step for subsequent model refinement and scenario analysis. The dataset is sourced entirely from publicly available and accessible outlets such as National and international organizations' websites, databases, journal articles, and existing modelling studies. This ensures that the dataset can be easily updated with the latest information or more precise local data. These data were utilized to calibrate a straightforward energy system model using the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS), incorporating three simplified scenarios The Business As Usual (BAU), Net Zero emission CO₂ by 2065 (NZ), and Renewable Scenario (REW) collectively highlight Rwanda's commitment of maximizing the use of renewable energy with the aim of reducing carbon dioxide (CO₂).

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The assumptions made and outcomes of these scenarios are outlined in the methodology.

1. Introduction

Energy modeling by using OSeMOSYS tool was very helpful, as it helped to assess how can Rwanda maximise renewable energy use. Electricity is one of the key pillars of Rwanda's sustainable development, where the Government is making efforts to increase the generation capacity and distribution throughout the country as outlined by least cost power development plan (REG, 2023).

GoR faces several energy challenges:

- Access to Finance
- Consumer Awareness
- Skills Development

Rwanda has a goal of 100% electricity access by 2024. However currently we have **52.2%** of renewable energy according to Electricity Generation mix, 2023, which consists predominantly of hydropower and solar.

Research Question:

1. How can Rwanda maximise the use of renewable energy with the aim of reducing carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions to mitigate climate change?
2. What would be the energy mix under a full renewable energy by 2065 under a least cost basis?

Results from the energy modelling performed using OSeMOSYS inform policy makers about required measures and evaluate the impact of different strategies on energy security, environmental sustainability, and economic development.

2. Methodology

Via this report, the use of energy modelling tools assists in identifying potential supply gaps and vulnerabilities in the energy system. Modelling tools like OSeMOSYS allow us to assess the environmental impact of energy choices. With energy modelling, it is possible to evaluate greenhouse gas emissions, air pollution, and other environmental factors associated with different energy pathways, With the increasing penetration of renewable energy sources (such as solar and wind).

By using the OSeMOSYS model, three scenarios were evaluated: the Business-As-Usual (BAU) scenario, the Renewable (REW) scenario and the Net Zero CO₂ Emission. The data used for these scenarios were obtained from Hydro power potential (Geoffre, 2018). This model and its outcomes are designed to serve as a

demonstration of what can be generated using the specific data available for Rwanda as detailed in one of the articles, and as a foundation for advancing further model development. The electricity demand profile is sourced from the PLEXOS dataset, estimating demand across 8 time slices.

Table 1 summarizes the main characteristics of these scenarios. Business As Usual (BAU) This is the baseline energy framework at a least cost basis for Rwanda energy system and it provides a reference for other scenarios (REG,2023). The second scenario is that of Net Zero Emission (NZ) with regards to Constrain Annual Emission Limits for CO2 to reach zero by 2065 (Governance, 2022). And finally, the third scenario is that of Renewable (REW) which is Targeting Zero new investment in fossil fuel technologies.

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
Reference scenario (BAU)	Model and understand expansion in the business as usual.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No carbon targets This is the baseline energy framework at a least cost basis for Rwanda energy system and it provides a reference for other scenarios
Net Zero emission (NZ)	A linear annual emission constraint, whereby zero emissions are achieved by 2065.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Constrained Annual Emission Limits for CO2 to reach zero by 2065.
Renewable (REW)	Promote renewable technologies in energy mix of Rwanda	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zero new investment in fossil fuel technologies (Light Fuel Oil Power Plant, Oil Fired Gas Turbine (SCGT), Gas Power Plant (CCGT), Gas Power Plant (SCGT), Light Fuel Oil Standalone Generator (1kW).

Table 1 - Summary of scenarios explored in the modelling.

3. Results

Figure 1. Power generation 2015-2065 by technology (PJ)

Figure 2. Installed capacity 2015-2065 by technology.

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Figure 3. Total Emissions 2015-2065 by technology.

Figure 4. Total Cost for BAU, REW and NZ(MUSD).

5. Discussion

As energy consumption grows, power generation also increases across all scenarios. Figure 1 illustrates the progressive augmentation in power generation, in the BAU, REW, and NZ scenarios, respectively. Both scenarios highlight the significance of hydro and Solar PV generation in supporting the growth in electricity supply by 2065. Figure 2 illustrates the

installed capacity progressively from 2015 up to 2065 and both scenarios highlight how and which technologies that are being installed based on the goal of maximizing the Renewable energy use. Rwandan government has a target of net zero CO₂ emissions by 2050 but has yet defined a Paris agreement decarbonization pathway but the Figure 3 demonstrates how the BAU, REW, NZ scenarios contribute to Zero Emission and it shows that both scenarios that emission reduction is feasible.

The total costs which are shown by the figure 4, for the BAU, NZ, and REW scenarios are estimated at 83783.7MUSD, 87237.4MUSD, and 93717.9MUSD, respectively. So, if the target is maximization of the use of renewable energy technologies mix by 2065 then we have to make an effort for investing more in renewable energy technologies so that we can get to the goal of Zero emission by 2065.

The reliance on fossil fuels decreases, indicating a strong push towards decarbonisation and sustainable energy. The Net Zero emission (NZ) scenario shows a major shift towards renewable energy sources, with a strong focus on reducing or eliminating fossil fuel usage. This shift is driven by enhanced Zero emission measures and the adoption of renewable energy technologies.

Future work associated with this study should focus on several key aspects to enhance the comprehensiveness and applicability of our findings. Firstly, a rigorous data review and continuous updates are imperative to ensure the accuracy and relevance of the model. Additionally, conducting a flexibility assessment will provide valuable insights into the system's ability to adapt to increasing shares of variable energy sources. The implementation of storage modelling represents another critical avenue for exploration, enabling a clearer understanding of the role of energy storage technologies in the Zero emission CO₂ journey. Lastly, a robustness analysis should be undertaken to evaluate the resilience of the proposed scenarios under various uncertainties. Addressing these future aspects will contribute to a more robust and actionable framework for guiding the transition to a zero emission Co₂ in Rwanda.

Conclusion

In order to maximize the use of renewable energy with the target of reducing CO₂ emissions to mitigate climate change, The analysis shows that the Business as usual(BAU) Renewable Energy (REW) and Net Zero emission (NZ) scenarios offer substantial benefits in terms of reducing CO₂ emissions and transitioning towards sustainable energy systems since it demonstrate that the renewable energies such as Hydro, Solar PV and Geothermal are dominating fossil fuel technologies such as Oil, Natural gas. For the total emission, analysis shows that the emission CO₂ on both scenarios is getting down especially on the Net Zero scenario, which is clearly supporting the target of Net zero emission by 2065.

Recommendations:

- Prioritize capacity building, research, and technological innovation in the energy sector.

- Policies should encourage private investment in renewable energy projects, including solar, wind, and geothermal.
- Developing infrastructure (grid expansion, transmission lines, and storage facilities) is essential for maximizing renewable energy utilization.
- Public awareness campaigns can promote renewable energy adoption.
- Explore new energy storage solutions, grid management techniques, and decentralized energy systems.

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